

HORIZON 2020

Coordination and Support Action

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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable 4.10

Guidelines and mechanism for evaluating impact

Submission of Deliverable

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1. Introduction

This Evaluation Framework is the tool to help communicators working in the EU-PolarNet consortium to demonstrate the impact of their work as part of the Communication and Engagement strategy (D4.3) that aims to connect EU-PolarNet participants with a number of target stakeholder groups.

Objectives of this strategy include:

- Identify stakeholder needs from target sectors within the EU-PolarNet community
- Facilitate effective dialogue between stakeholders and researchers to exchange views on the priority polar research issues
- Create appropriate channels and mechanisms to involve stakeholders in the co-design of research proposals that have outcomes directly relevant and beneficial to society and business

This Framework builds on the latest industry best practice. It enables EU-PolarNet consortium members to adopt a clear and consistent approach to evaluation across all stakeholder engagement activities, however especially with stakeholder groups. It is also designed to reflect the integrated nature of modern communications where all areas of communications have a part to play. This Framework should be used as a helpful reference guide when planning an activity and setting metrics to track EU-PolarNet's success, delivering against the project's communication objectives and goals. It contains a recommended core set of measures for each communication discipline to ensure the evaluation is consistent and the right metrics are used.

2. How this framework will be used

What this framework is for

This Evaluation Framework supports a more consistent approach to evaluation across the EU-PolarNet community, where outcomes are aligned to objectives. The Framework provides consortium members with a set of valid evaluation measures – outputs, outtakes and outcomes – to collect, analyse and report on for each type of communications activity against each of the stakeholder groups as identified in the stakeholder 'map' (D4.5)

Users of the framework

This Evaluation Framework will be used by all EU-PolarNet Communicators during the planning stages of communications activities. Considering evaluation at an early stage in the communications planning process provides the opportunity to benchmark, track the right metrics and conduct robust and comprehensive evaluation.

How the framework will be used

Engagement leads will select the areas of communications that they are using – in this case stakeholder groups. With the so called SMART communications objectives (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Timely) and target audience in mind, they will select

the relevant metrics across outputs, outtakes, outcomes and organisational impact to understand how a specific activity has performed. Not every activity will require data capture on every metric, but the EU-PolarNet will consider a range of metrics and a mix of qualitative and quantitative evidence to help ensure robust and credible evaluation. Available data and audience insight will be used to set benchmarks and targets. The EU-PolarNet communicators will further set processes to collect data against the selected metrics in place regularly, adding context by analysing change over time. Review performance and ensure evaluation insights are fed into live activity and future planning.

3. The Golden Rules of Evaluation

4. Stakeholder Engagement

Evidence of the impact of the activities outlined by each organisation should be summarised in brief one-two page evaluation reports under the headers listed below. Numbers to demonstrate quantitative impact (such as how much press coverage a press release achieved or how many people attended an event) are as important as qualitative impact (such as what people said and their actions following an activity).

Inputs	Outputs	Outtakes	Outcomes	Organisational impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key steps of objective, audience, strategy and implementation Costs (eg staff, agencies) Content creation (eg consultations, correspondence, e-newsletters) Pre-engagement activities (ie stakeholder mapping, prioritisation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Item of stakeholder comms delivered (eg letters, newsletter, email updates) Target audience reached (ie directly or via stakeholder comms channels) Partners/priority stakeholders secured Channels used (ie earned) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness Message recall Purpose recognition Audience engagement (eg enquiry calls, click throughs, shares, likes, retweets, downloads) Responses & Feedback (eg comments, letters) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder satisfaction rating Advocacy (eg recommendations, endorsements) Productive partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to Project Goals or Key Performance Indicators: Increased no of partnerships or collaborations More funding

Example: EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event – “Towards the 1.5°C climate goal – Perspectives from the Polar Regions”

Activity details:	
Type of activity	Town Hall Event
Title of activity	EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event – “Towards the 1.5°C climate goal – Perspectives from the Polar Regions”
Date and location	27 th September 2016; Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels (Belgium)
Attendees	<i>Please attach list of participants</i>
Agenda	<i>Please attach agenda</i>
Input	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore how polar research can deliver tangible benefits for European society, especially with regard to the 1.5°C climate goal. Initiating milestone in EU-PolarNet’s stakeholder dialogue.

Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European national and international policymakers based in Brussels; - business representatives; - indigenous people; - media; - European scientific community
Strategy and implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selecting venue in vicinity to the European Parliament and the European Commission. - High-level keynote speakers and panel, representing the targeted audience. - Evening reception with art installation. - Personalised invitations.
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Venue: 4.682 € - Catering: 5.289,11 - Travel reimbursements: - Live stream: 1.500 €
Content creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opening video - Information package
Pre-engagement activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder mapping - Topic consultation with European Commission
Output	
Item of stakeholder comms delivered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Newsletter - Website page - Live stream - Meeting report
Target audience reached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Directly via invitation to events, live stream, newsletter. - Indirectly via stakeholder newsletters.
Partners/priority stakeholders secured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indigenous people: Sami representation; - National and international policy makers: members of the European Commission and European parliament; - Media: Brussels based journalists - Business: shipping representative
Channels used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media: YouTube, Facebook and Twitter - Email - Website
Outtakes	
Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 108 participants from 18 countries and European and international organizations attended the Town Hall event. - More than 300 recipients of newsletter summarizing the event.
Message recall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urgent need for the European community to prioritize polar issues, face the associated challenges and better estimate the impact of climate and environmental changes in the Polar Regions. - Increased collaboration with indigenous peoples and local communities is vital to understand processes in the high latitudes, to predicting future changes and to finding appropriate mitigation and adaptation measures. These collaborations require sustained relationships that build on mutual respect and trust. - Economic development in the high latitudes calls for a holistic Arctic policy that guarantees sustainable utilization of resources, protects the sensitive ecosystems and fosters innovative technologies. - Improved public engagement and open and transparent communication is needed in order to enhance an understanding of why the changes occurring in the Polar Regions are important

	globally and how mitigation efforts in the lower latitudes in turn affect and benefit the higher latitudes.
Audience engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active discussions during the event. - Around 250 views on YouTube. - 60 individual tweets used #EUPolarPriorities, with each tweet getting retweeted/favorited between 1-8 times. Over 11.000 organic impressions (times tweets were viewed), 200 engagements (times someone clicked on links, hashtags, etc.), 33 retweets and 37 likes.
Outcomes	
Stakeholder satisfaction rating	n/a
Reputation rating	n/a
Advocacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conference statement was delivered and feeds back to recommendations for informed decision-making and future funding priorities.
Attitude change	n/a
Productive partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established lasting relationship with key representatives of Sami community, shipping industry and European policy makers
Organisational impact	
Contribution to project goals and objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Showcased need for improved and strengthened international cooperation in polar research; - Milestone towards Integrated European Polar Research Programme; - Initiated dialogic stakeholder engagement;

5. Recommendations

Actions:

- Engagement leaders who have already organised and delivered stakeholder events should use these guidelines to produce brief evaluation reports (one page) and submit them to the EU-PolarNet project manager and respective work package leader.
- Engagement leaders who are planning future stakeholder events should use these guidelines to set out the aims and objectives of each event and how they will evaluate and report on success or otherwise.